

Syntheses of Some Arylsulphonyl Pyrazolines and Pyrazolones as Potential Antipyretic Analgesic Agents

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Treatment of 3-methyl or 3-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (1a, b) with *p*-acetamido or *p*-methylbenzenesulphonyl chloride afforded the O-sulphonyl derivatives (3a-d). The *N*-sulphonyl derivative (6) and *N*-methyl derivative (8) were also prepared. The 3-anilino derivatives (10a-d) and 3,5-dimethylpyrazoline derivative (13) were prepared. The ir spectral data of the synthesised compounds are discussed.

In recent years, there has been intensive activity involving the synthesis and investigation of the biological activity of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones. Derivatives of these compounds have been extensively studied for their importance as antipyretics and analgesics¹. Various pyrazolinones have been claimed to be effective as germicides and fungicides.

As a further extension of our recent work²⁻⁵, our first interest was focused on the synthesis of some sulphonyl derivatives of expected biological activity.

It has been reported that, 3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1) on treatment with *p*-acetamidobenzenesulphonyl chloride in pyridine gave (2)⁹. In contrast to this we obtain the O-sulphonyl derivative (3), as inferred from the absence of the carbonyl and NH absorptions for the pyrazolone and the appearance of a band at 1385 and 1200 cm⁻¹ (-O-SO₂-).

Similarly, treatment of 1a with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in pyridine afforded 3b, which was inferred from (i) ir spectrum which showed absorption band at 1390 and 1200 cm⁻¹ (-O-SO₂-) and (ii) boiling with alcoholic potassium hydroxide to give 1a.

The behaviour of the same reagents towards 3-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1b) was also investigated to give compounds 3c and 3d. The structure of compounds (3c) and (3d) was confirmed from (i) ir spectra and (ii) boiling with alcoholic potassium hydroxide to give (1b).

An attempt was made to obtain the *N*-sulphonyl analogue (4), upon treatment of ethyl acetoacetate with benzenesulphonylhydrazide in hot ethanolic solution, but the only product obtained was *s*-diphenylsulphonylhydrazine (5). Confirmatory evidence for the formation of 5 was provided from (i) analytical data, (ii) identity of its m.p. with that reported in literature and (iii) authentic sample, prepared from hydrazine sulphate and benzenesulphonyl chloride¹⁰ or heating benzenesulphonylhydrazide with water.

On the otherhand, the *N*-sulphonyl analogue (6) was now obtained from the condensation of ethyl α -phenylhydrazonobenzoyl acetate with benzenesulphonylhydrazide.

Compound (6) showed the following characteristic band: 1325 cm⁻¹ assigned to S=O asym. stretching vibration of medium intensity; sharp bands of equal intensities at 1160 and 1070 cm⁻¹ assigned to N-SO₂ and S=O sym. stretching vibration, respectively; 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O); 1600 cm⁻¹

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(C=N); and 3500 cm^{-1} (NH). Boiling of compound **6** with alcoholic potassium hydroxide afforded 3-phenyl-4-phenylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one (**7**)¹¹.

The behaviour of the compound **7** towards methylation was also investigated. Thus treatment of **7** with dimethylsulphate afforded 1-methyl-3-phenyl-4-phenylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one (**8**).

The ir spectrum of compound **8** showed well defined bands at 1450 ($-\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 1600 (C=N), 1690 (C=O) and a broad band extending from 3300 to 3500 cm^{-1} (NH).

As an extension to the synthesis of the *N*-sulphonyl derivatives, treatment of ethyl α -phenylthiocarbonyl glyoxalate arylhydrazones (**9a-d**)¹² with benzenesulphonylhydrazide in ethanolic solution afforded 1-phenylsulphonyl-3-anilino-4-arylhya-zono-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (**11a-d**). Their ir spectra

showed absorption at 1670 - 1690 (CO), 3300 - 3400 (NH), 1590 - 1610 (C=N) and 1160 cm^{-1} (N-SO₂).

The formation of **10a-d** may have involved the condensation of the thio carbonyl thione group with benzenesulphonylhydrazide followed by the cyclisation of the intermediate formed (*cf.* route a). This is in analogy to the reported¹³ behaviour of thioamides of benzoylacetic acid towards the action of hydroxylamine and hydrazines. The possibility of an initial formation of a hydrazide intermediate followed by cyclisation with the thione group (*cf.* route b) leading to the same product (**10**) cannot be overlooked. However, in support of the formation of **10**, we have found that treatment of **10a-d** with alcoholic potassium hydroxide afforded 3-anilino-4-arylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (**11a-d**)¹¹.

1-Phenylsulphonyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazopyrazoline (**13**) was obtained from the condensation of β -phenylazoacetyl acetone (**12**) with benzenesulphonylhydrazide. No carbonyl absorption appeared in its ir spectra. Further evidence for the formation of **13** is provided from the formation of **14** upon treatment of **13** with alcoholic potassium hydroxide. An authentic sample of **14** was prepared from **12** and hydrazine, its m.p. is identical with that obtained.

Studies of the pharmacotoxicological activities of compounds **3**, **6**, **8**, **10** and **13** are still under investigation.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in a Gallen-kamp electric melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were performed on a Unicam SP 2000 infrared spectrophotometer.

Condensation of 3 methyl or 3-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1a, b) with p-acetamidobenzenesulphonyl chloride and/or p-toluenesulphonyl chloride: Formation of 3a-d; General procedures: A mixture of **1a** or **1b** (0.01 mol) and *p*-acetamidobenzenesulphonyl chloride or *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (0.11 mol) in pyridine (30 ml), was refluxed for 4 h, left to cool, poured into ice-cold water and the solid products

obtained were crystallised from dilute ethanol. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compd no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Formula (Mol. wt.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	S
3a	193	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO ₄ (295.306)	49.11 (48.80)	4.35 (4.43)	14.41 (14.22)	10.91 (10.85)
3b	105	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ SO ₃ (252.296)	52.61 (52.36)	4.59 (4.79)	11.41 (11.10)	12.91 (12.70)
3c	215	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ SO ₄ (357.376)	57.41 (57.13)	4.11 (4.23)	11.85 (11.75)	9.21 (8.97)
3d	107	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO ₂ (314.356)	61.41 (61.12)	4.52 (4.48)	9.11 (8.91)	10.41 (10.20)

Condensation of ethyl acetoacetate with benzene-sulphonhydrazide; Formation of s-diphenylsulphonylhydrazine (5): A mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mol) and benzenesulphonhydrazide (0.011 mol) in 95% ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, and left to stand overnight. The solid product obtained was crystallised from ethanol to give compound 5 as white crystals (80%), m.p. 245° (Found : C, 46.21 ; H, 3.91 ; N, 9.11 ; S, 20.32. C₁₂H₁₂N₂S₂O₄ (312.37) calcd. C, 46.13 ; H, 3.87 ; N, 8.97 ; S, 0.53%).

Preparation of an authentic sample of s-diphenylsulphonylhydrazine (5): Benzenesulphonhydrazide (0.5 g) in water (30 ml) was boiled for 1 h and the solid product obtained after cooling was crystallised from ethanol to give compound 5, m.p. 245°.

1-Phenylsulphonyl-3-phenyl-4-phenylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one (6): A mixture of ethyl α -phenylhydrazonobenzoyl acetate (0.01 mol) and benzenesulphonhydrazide (0.011 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h, and left to cool. The solid product obtained was crystallised from ethanol to give compound 6 yield (75%), m.p. 190° (Found : C, 62.41 ; H, 3.85 ; N, 13.95 ; S, 7.89. C₂₁H₁₆N₄SO₃ (404.436) calcd. C, 62.36 ; H, 3.98 ; N, 13.85 ; S, 7.92%).

3-Phenyl-4-phenylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one (7): Compound 6 (0.5 g) was refluxed in 4% alcoholic KOH (30 ml) for 1 h. The mixture was then poured while hot into ice-cold dilute acetic acid. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol to give compound 7, m.p. 208°¹¹.

1-Methyl-3-phenyl-4-phenylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-one (8): Compound 7 (0.01 mol) was heated with dimethyl sulphate (0.02 mol) for 5 min, cooled, poured onto ice-cold sodium hydroxide solution (30%). The product that separated was filtered and crystallised from methanol to give compound 8 yield (65%), m.p. 138° (Found : C, 69.92 ; H, 5.17 ; N, 20.24. C₁₆H₁₄N₄O (278.30) calcd. C, 69.04 ; H, 5.07 ; N, 20.13%).

1-Phenylsulphonyl-3-anilino-4-arylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (10a-d): To ethyl α -phenylthiocarbamylglyoxalate arylhydrazones (9a-d, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), was added benzenesulphonhydrazide (0.011 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed until no hydrogen sulphide gas evolved and left to cool. The solid product obtained was filtered off

and crystallised from ethanol to give compounds 10a-d. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Compd no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Formula (Mol. wt.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	S
10a	170	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₅ SO ₃ (419.456)	60.41 (60.12)	4.30 (4.08)	7.53 (7.64)
10b	123	60	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₅ SO ₃ (433.476)	60.83 (60.95)	4.62 (4.40)	7.43 (7.62)
10c	112	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ SO ₃ (433.476)	61.11 (60.95)	4.64 (4.40)	7.51 (7.62)
10d	118	85	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ SO ₄ (449.476)	59.03 (58.78)	4.50 (4.26)	7.11 (7.13)

*3-Anilino-4-arylhydrazono-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (11a-d)*¹¹: In 4% alcoholic potassium hydroxide, 10 (0.5 g) was refluxed for 1 h and then poured while hot into ice-cold dilute acetic acid. The solid products obtained were crystallised from ethanol to give compounds 11a-d. The m.p.s were in agreement with those reported in literature¹¹.

1-Phenylsulphonyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-phenyl azopyrazolin (13): A mixture of β -phenylazoacetyl acetone (0.01 mol) and benzenesulphonhydrazide (0.011 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h and left to cool. The solid product obtained was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give compound 13 as a yellow crystals (65%), m.p. 190° (Found : C, 60.11 ; H, 4.65 ; N, 16.53 ; S, 9.66. C₁₇H₁₆N₄SO₂ (340.596) calcd. C, 59.98 ; H, 4.73 ; N, 16.46 ; S, 9.42%).

Treatment of 13 with alcoholic potassium hydroxide; Formation of 14: In 4% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (30 ml), 13 (0.3 g) was refluxed for 2 h and then poured while hot into ice-cold dilute acetic acid. The solid product obtained was filtered to give m.p. identical with that reported in literature¹¹.

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